

DETERMINANTS OF ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AMONG SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN IN 21ST CENTURY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

Indu Singh* & Amiteshwar Ratra**

*Research Scholar, Staff Training and Research Institute of Distance Education, Indira Gandhi National Open University, New Delhi.

**Associate Professor in Distance Education, Staff Training and Research Institute of Distance Education, Indira Gandhi National Open University, New Delhi

Corresponding Author: Dr. Amiteshwar Ratra, STRIDE, IGNOU, New Delhi.

Abstract

Education is a tool which leads to academic growth of school going children in this 21st century and that motivates them to greater achievements in their later lives. Motivation is necessary for accomplishment of any task, test and helps in achievement. Motivation encourages school going children to achieve good marks/grades in their examinations. Motivation differs for each child as every individual has unique abilities and coping strategies. Motivation could be intrinsic motivation in some children or extrinsic motivation in others. Achievement motivation is said to also be influenced by parental behaviour. The objective of the paper is to assess the achievement motivation among school going children in 21st century and examines the determinants therein through existing literature. The methodology of the paper is qualitative data analysis based on the secondary data. This paper attempts to conduct a document analysis of research published in this context. Based on the objective of this study, 16 papers were extensively examined. It was found that achievement motivation was influenced by conservative attitudes and prejudgments attached to various situations. Further, it was seen that student participation in various co-curricular activities at school level can help them to improve their reasoning and problem-solving skills that strive to achieve high aspirations. Some of the suggestions to enhance achievement motivation among the school students have been highlighted in the end of the paper. Parents should listen to their children and attempt to solve issues concerning the child's problems, and concerns through discussions. Parent-child communication and learning from online mode has become important factors for achievement motivation for the 21st century school students.

Key Words: Achievement motivation, school going children, online learning, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, school students.

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INTRODUCTION

In 21st century, schools at all levels take efforts to strengthen students academically that inspired them to excel in school. Children's Level of intelligence, performance, and achievement in the classroom are all

influenced by motivation factors(Dhanya & Anitha2013).The achievement of an individual is extremely associated with the extent of motivation he or she has(Dhanya & Anitha2013).Colleges and schools have become increasingly demanding in their admissions processes, scrutinizing not only high school academic records, but also student engagement in co-curricular activities(Dhanya & Anitha2013).So, the emphasis was given on the understanding of the characteristics that promotes high levels of educational performance and potentials among high school students that has motivated researchers to look beyond the limitations of individual thought and investigate their individual performances(Dhanya & Anitha2013).

The motivation of the students creates a learning atmosphere that encourages or hinders learning beyond what would be expected depending on their achievement motivation, intelligence, and other characteristics (Dhanya & Anitha2013). The present study examines the determinants of achievement motivation among school going children in the 21st century.

The objectives of the paper are:

- To find out the determinants associated with the achievement motivation among the school going children in the 21st century.
- To give suggestions to overcome the challenges of achievement motivation among the school going children in the 21st century.

METHODOLOGY

The present study is based on the qualitative data. Various research papers were collated, and their document analysis was done keeping in view the objectives of this study. Analysis of the collated review material was done.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theories of motivation

Woolfolk (2013) defined “motivation as an internal condition that arouses, directs, and maintains behavior.” There are a variety of theories of motivation, including

Theory of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation: Ryan and Deci (2000) affirm that intrinsic motivation refers to a behavior that is driven by self-satisfaction rather than external anticipation. Intrinsic motivation is founded on the desire to control, curiosity, fantasy, and challenge. In the classroom, a lot of will power and a positive attitude are required to keep motivation going.

Ryan and Deci (2000) declare self-determination theory as both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The intrinsic motivation defines the activities which are done for the sake of personal benefits and enjoyment and extrinsic motivation represents the external aspects of individual which is getting reward or something. ARCS Model -Attention, Relevance, Confidence and Satisfaction attributes model. Wlodkowski (1978) stated that motivation is related to behavior and emotion. Students are motivated directly by grabbing the students' attention by using a stimulating and attractive media. Motivating students directly can be achieved through providing them with engaging, stimulating, and enjoyable learning materials. It is important to hold the attention of the learners and to engage them in the learning, and to engage them in' experiences,

and the demands of the learners make learning relevant. It could be interpreted as ODL learning material must be provided to distance learners to encourage learners to keep learning.

Social Cognitive Theory: Bandura (1989) proposed “the social cognitive theory. Social cognitive theory depicts the interrelationship between behavior, environment factor as well as personal influences. Social Cognitive theory is the study of how knowledge is acquired through interaction through observation, experience, and the influence of outside media. Social Cognitive theory refers to the capacity to create meaning and knowledge from social influences. Social cognitive theory can be utilized across a variety of fields including communication, education psychology, psychotherapy, and psychology.

Expectancy Theory: Eerde and Thierry (1996) explained Vroom's expectancy model. The theory was developed in the context of work to inspire employees. The theory is based upon motivation, and it is interlinked. It is believed that there is a relationship between effort and performance. Employees who put in the effort are rewarded and appreciated.

Determinants of Achievement Motivation

Demographic factors such as age, gender, ethnicity, and home play an important impact on student motivation and engagement. The study reveals that the resources of the household and parenting style plays an important role in the development of children motivation. The most important parental and home factors that contribute to characteristics of success which are motivation and engagement according to the Mansour, M., & Martin, A.(2009). Chow, S.J.& Yong. B. C. S. (2013) found a moderate level of intrinsic motivation, individual significance, and self-determination in the field of learning science stream. Also, found significant difference between the motivation of boys and girls toward learning science stream and difference between the high and low achieving students of science stream.

According to the Akpan, I.D. & Umobong, M.E. (2013) motivation has high impact on students' academic engagement. Additionally, male students were highly motivated than female student and, age is also a factor. The authors N. Dhanya & Anitha (2013) compared the achievement motivation of high school students of Ernakulam district in Kerala where they assessed the need to succeed in the areas of academic success ,vocational and skill achievement where girls are doing better than boys.

Kumar, A. & Yadav, D.(2015) in their study found out that students from government schools were less motivated than private school students at senior secondary level. The study of Mishra, H. P. (2017) reveals the no significant difference in relation to the demographic factors(location, gender) and achievement motivation of secondary school students.

The study of Solanki V. N. (2017) discovered that the main effect of urban and rural areas, types of schools, gender, and achievement motivation on study habits was significantly different. According to Anita, P., & Jebaseelan S. U. (2018) motivation may differ depending upon the individual variables i.e., the socioeconomic status, location of residence and gender. Naite, I. (2018) study concluded that Thai students were highly academically proficient and high achievers. And the psychological factors are an important factor that influence the academic success of the student. However, motivation and self-regulation, academic self-perception and attitude toward teachers and classes were found significant predictors of

academic achievement. Academic achievement was heavily affected by gender, grade level, parental education, and parents' educational level.

According to Santhi & Suthanthiradevi (2019) more than two-fifths of secondary students at government schools can demonstrate moderate levels of motivation. Achievement motivation categorized according to the profile of that school children as gender, class level, kinds of schools, father and mother education and family income monthly. Darsana Changkakoti, D.& Baishya, P. (2020) in the current study described that the main goal is to find out the correlation between level of aspiration as well as motivation for achievement of higher secondary students however, the results show that no significant relationship exists between the aspiration and motivation of higher secondary schools.

Rani, P., & Reddy, R. G. (2019) in their research found that there was a substantial difference in the achievement motivation of students in sciences and arts stream and between college students. According to the study of Soni, A. R. (2013) Students are less motivated and has found no significant relation with the home environment. Muola, J. M. (2010) used two questionnaires for data collection where he accesses the home environment factors related with achievement motivation of the students where results show no significant relation is there. Kaur, S. (2013) discovered that achievement motivation was high in school students in relation to their academic achievement.

According to the study of Bharanbe, K. D. (2016) the significant difference was found between the secondary school students of private and government school where private school students have high motivation in comparison to government school students. Hooja, H. R., & Shaktawat, P. (2017) analyzed data by using regression and correlation through SPSS and results revealed that there is negative effect of home environment on psychological well-being that affects achievement motivation and further stated that the home environment & achievement is correlated.

Table 1: Significant Researches pertaining to determinants of achievement motivation

Research Publication	Research Finding
Mansour, M., & Martin, A.(2009)	demographic factors like home play an important impact on student motivation and engagement
Chow, S.J.& Yong. B. C. S.(2013)	moderate level intrinsic motivation, personal relevance, and self-determination in the field of learning-combined science stream.
Akpan, I.D. & Umobong, M.E.(2013)	motivation has influenced motivated students' academic engagement more than the less motivated students
N. Dhanya & Anitha(2013)	Students need to succeed in the areas of academic success as well as vocational and skill achievement
Kumar, A. & Yadav, D.(2015)	students from government schools were less motivated than private school students at senior secondary level

Mishra, H .P.(2017)	significant differences in achievement motivation based on location , but there were no significant differences in relation to gender.
Solanki. N.(2017)	main effect of urban and rural areas, types and schools, gender, and achievement motivation on study habits and motivation was significant
Anita, P., & Jebaseelan, S. U.(2018)	motivation to succeed may differ depending on the individual variables i.e., the socioeconomic status, location of residence and gender.
Naite, I.(2018)	psychological factors are an important factor that influence the academic success of the student
Santhi & Suthanthiradevi (2019)	two-fifths of secondary students at government schools can demonstrate moderate levels of motivation
Darsana Changkakoti, D.& Baishya, P. (2020)	correlation between level of aspiration as well as motivation for achievement of higher secondary students
Soni, A. R.(2013)	Motivation in academic work is significantly determined by the nature of their home environment.
Muola, J. M.(2010).	No significant relationship between the achievement motivation and home environment of the students.
Kaur, S.(2013).	Academic Achievement is high in relation to the achievement motivation of school going children
Bharanbe, K. D.(2016).	Achievement motivation was high in private school students in comparison to government school students.
Hooja, H. R., & Shaktawat, P. (2017).	Study shows correlation between psychological well-being and achievement motivation

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that as shown through various studies determinants of achievement motivation has a significant relationship with the demographic conditions, aspirational level of students, and types of schools. Impact on the academic engagement of students that motivated them to engage in the activities and they take part in at school, which leads to high academic results. Some students are not able to perform due to the psycho-social factors like tension, stress, or depression from receiving poor grades in every subject that determine their stream at higher levels and gender variation in the streams. Need for self-learning skills which only comes within self , it comes during the leisure time or time management and technology should be used in the learning which creates learning creative and joyful.

Fig 1: Determinants of Achievement Motivation: Relationships between academics and achievement motivation of school students

SUGGESTIONS

Some suggestions for overcoming the challenges of achievement motivation among school-going children are as follows:

Students motivated to use technology

Access to technology in India by students are less in number due to the large number of populations living in rural areas of India. In urban areas of India students easily access the learning platforms and motivates towards online learning. Family should support them so that they can learn by their own. Because of the lockdown the schools switch to online learning.

Interaction through online learning

We make sure that students find ways to communicate and connect to continue online learning. It promotes collaboration and empowerment. Online learning is playing an important role in the teaching-learning. Online education becomes necessity as education system is virtually available now a days and due to pandemic, it was compulsion to teach online by following certain guidelines and using online teaching-learning, the most important aspect is missing i.e., pedagogy (Panda, 2020)

Importance of leisure

Some students should know the importance of quality leisure time which will be utilized in a positive manner as it develops some psychological skills and cognitive wellbeing. It helps in positive outlook towards developing skills and these coping skills may help them to reduce stress and achieve good grades in academics and gain motivation.

Self-motivation to self-learning

Students know their capabilities to learn by managing time for each activity and it was all done by doing

self-learning : self-learning is what a person learn with or without any assistance and diagnose their learning needs and formulating goals and search for resources and after that evaluate their learning based on that.

Socialization towards school activities

Participation in various activities can help students improve their reasoning and problem-solving skills. Students must strive to achieve high aspirations. Aspiration is the key to high performance. Teachers and parents must set high standards for their students. However, it is crucial to be aware of the gender, age, and intellectual standards of students. Achievement motivation is influenced by parental behavior. Parents should listen to their children and attempt to solve all their problems, questions, and concerns. Motivation to achieve is influenced by conservative attitudes and prejudgments attached to various situations. Students are often motivated to accomplish more because of their attitudes and preconceived notions.

Requirement of training for in-service teachers

The teacher must clearly communicate the concept and emphasize the student's understanding. They should be concerned about students who are not performing well in class and be able to assist students by encouraging them to participate in academic activities. Motivation to succeed can be enhanced through training programs of in-service teachers to equip them with the necessary abilities and skills to boost the motivation of students to succeed. Teachers training of using technology which is the requirement in this virtual era where teaching -learning turned into online learning.

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